

Assessment of the Financial Feasibility of a 30MW Biomass Plant in Ghana

Jerome Dela Lavie

Kwame Nkrumah University of Science & Technology, Ghana

27th May 2024

Executive Summary

Globally, the race is on to transition from crude energy sources to clean, renewable and sustainable sources. With the imminent dangers of climate change many countries have found innovative ways to convert waste to energy to reduce emissions, which is in line with the Paris Accord of which Ghana is a signatory. Ghana is still heavily reliant on fossil fuel sources for energy generation. The purpose of this study was to assess the financial viability of a 30MW biomass plant to be situated in Ejura for 25 years using a financial modelling tool (FINPLAN™). Three scenarios, ie. varying plant generation capacity, levelized cost of energy and fuel cost were simulated using the tool to observe their effects on Net Present Value (NPV), Internal Rate of Return (IRR) and Shareholders Dividends. The results showed that for the proposed 30MW power plant to be financially viable, the minimum generation capacity allowed is 50%. ie 100GWh, the energy produced should be sold at \$0.085 to make maximum gains. It estimates that fuel cost for running operations should not exceed \$4M for good returns. For the sustainability of the project government must enforce its environmental pollution laws to ensure there is constant supply of fuel for the plant.

Keywords: Biomass; Renewable Energy; FinPlan; LCOE; Climate Change; Energy Financing

1. Introduction

Due to the imminent challenges of climate change across the globe, many countries have taken the initiative to reduce their over dependence on fossil fuels (United Nations, 2023). Several other countries in their quest to reduce emissions have found innovative ways to convert their waste into energy (Korneti, 2021; Ralls, 2023). Examples of such countries include Sweden, Denmark, Finland, Germany, Mozambique and South Africa.

However in Ghana the situation is the reverse. The environment is polluted each and everyday by the indiscriminate open burning of waste, improper disposal of waste and overburdened land fill sites which jeopardizes public health (SDG 3), contaminates water sources (SDG 6), and harms ecosystems (SDG 15) (Amuah *et al.*, 2024).

Although the power sector has seen a significant transformation over the years, it is heavily reliant on fossil fuel sources (Akrorful, 2022). According to Mawusi *et al.* (2023), Ghana generates 3 million tons of wood waste and 39 million tons of crop residues annually. In the wake of the challenges bedeviling the energy generation in Ghana, this biomass waste can serve as a feedstock for generating energy to augment the current capacity being generated. As a country with agricultural activities contributing about 19.57% to GDP (Statista, 2024), there are enormous sources of agricultural waste and forest residues that can be converted into energy. Currently, Ghana's power generation mix does not contain biomass sources on a large scale hence the need to explore this area.

This report presents a financial analysis specifically the viability of building a biomass power plant in Ejura Sekyedumase, an agricultural producing district in Ghana. The main objective of the study is to conduct a financial analysis of a 30MW biomass power plant in Ghana. Several scenarios will be interrogated while analyzing the sensitivity of the various scenarios.

Fig 1. Ejura Sekyedumase District

Fig 2. Biomass waste at Ejura

2. Methodology

2.1 Modelling Tool

The tool used for the study is the Model for Financial Analysis of Electric Sector Expansion Plans (FINPLAN) developed by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) for carrying out financial analysis of power projects. As an offline tool it requires the user to input certain information for a desired output. The input and output variables of the FINPLAN tool can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Input and Output data for the FINPLAN tool

Input	Output
Plant Size, Projected Generation, Life of plant	Balanced Sheets, Cashflow Statements
Cost of credit, Fuel Cost, O&M cost, etc	Shareholders statements
Loans, bonds, equity, etc	Financial Ratios
Exchange rates, Interest rate, Inflation rate, etc	

2.2 Data sources

Secondary data was mainly used for the study. Exchange rates, Discount rate, inflation rate for Ghana was obtained from the Bank of Ghana official website (Bank of Ghana, n.d.). Information on cost of export credit and terms was obtained from the official website of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, n.d.).

2.3 Assumptions

As a hypothetical plant, assumptions were made on fuel and Operations and maintenance Costs. As an independent power producer a tax rate of 25% was assumed. The project also assumed that 85% of the total investment would be financed by foreign export credit while the additional 15% will be obtained from local commercial loans.

2.3.1 Project Brief

Table 2 contains a summary of the proposed project; the plant data, financial and economic data some actual and some assumed that was used fed into the the FINPLAN tool.

Table 2. Project Description and Financing

Plant Data	Financial Data	Economic Data
Size: 30MW	85% of export credit over 12 years with uniform principal and interest repayment at 5.5% interest rate	Foreign Currency: USD Local Currency: GHC Inflation USD: 3%; Inflation GHC: 25%
Lifespan: 2025-2050	15% Commercial loans at interest rate of 30%	Discount rate: 23%
Location: Ejura Sekyedumase District, Ghana		
Generation: 200GWh/year	Short term deposits: interest rate -28% over inflation	Income Tax: 25%
Construction period: 3 years	Stand-by facility: interest rate 29% over inflation Total Investment: \$25M	Exchange rate- 1 USD: 15 GHC

2.4 Scenarios or sensitivity analysis

As seen in Fig 3. three different scenarios, i.e. varying plant production capacity, levelized cost of energy and adjusting the cost of fuel were developed to analyse the sensitivity on Net Present Value, Internal Rate of Return and Shareholders Dividends.

Fig 3. Scenarios and Sensitivity Analysis

3. Results

Scenarios and Sensitivity Analysis

3.1 Scenario 1: Varying Plant Production Capacity

In this scenario the plant production capacity was varied from 25%, 50%, 70%, 85% and 100% of the full annual production capacity of 200GWh to determine the effect on NPV, IRR and Shareholders dividends. As seen in Fig 4. IRR increases with increasing the capacity of the plant production capacity. Shareholders dividends also increases steadily as the plant capacity is increased. It can be observed that there is no dividend available for 25% plant capacity, which is undesirable for investors.

Fig 4a. Production capacity vs NPV vs IRR

Fig 4b. Production capacity vs Dividends

From Fig 4 it can be inferred that the plant should be operating at 50% capacity or more to be profitable.

3.2 Scenario 2: Varying Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE)

The second scenario focused on varying the cost of energy per kilowatt-hour while at the minimum profitable plant capacity of 100GWh. Which implies that any variation of price beyond 100GWh will be profitable. The prices was varied from \$0.025, \$0.045, \$0.065, \$0.085 to \$0.1 per kilowatt-hour observe the sensitivity. From Fig 5b it can be observed that prices below \$0.065/kWh will yield a negative NPV whereas prices above that yields a positive NPV and an attractive IRR of 34.3% Consequently Fig 5b shows LCOE of \$0.025/kWh and \$0.045/kWh not producing yields for investors. Whereas good returns for prices from 0.065/kWh and above recorded cumulative dividends from \$2.5M to \$6.5M.

Fig 5a. Levelized Cost of Energy vs NPV vs IRR

Fig 5b. LCOE vs Dividends

Based on the results of the analysis it can be inferred that energy prices above \$0.065/kWh at 50% annual plant production capacity will be profitable. Probing further, selling at a price of \$0.085/kWh gives a better debt service coverage. This implies that at maximum capacity at these prices will yield higher returns for investors.

3.3 Scenario 3: Varying Cost of Fuel

Scenario three of the analysis focused on varying the annual cost of fuel from a range of \$0M to \$8M by increments of \$2M for generating a minimum of 100GWh to be sold at \$0.085. Fig 6a shows the outcome of varying fuel cost on NPV, IRR and dividends.

A downward decreasing trend in NPV and IRR is observed for decreasing fuel cost. However, Fig 6b depicts increasing dividend values when fuel cost is reduced. As fuel costs kept rising, operations of the plant will yield no dividends for share holders. This is expected because decreasing fuel will reduce cost of production hence increasing profit margins.

Fig 6a. Fuel Cost vs NPV vs IRR

Fig 6b. Fuel Cost vs Dividends

■

The essence of this scenario is to observe the sensitivity of varying fuel cost for production, although agricultural waste could be obtained for free, some farmers when later realize the value of the waste may begin to demand some amount for their waste. The other component of the fuel component is the cost of potentially transporting feed stock from other parts of the country.

It can be inferred that low fuel costs will yield more interests for investors. This analogy is true for renewable energy projects like solar power plants whose source of fuel is the sun.

5. Discussion

The results of the sensitivity analysis has shown that for the 30MW biomass plant to be cost effective and viable, the plant capacity should be not less than 50%, i.e. 100GWh/year to achieve a positive NPV and a favorable IRR of 45.65% and above due to the high interest rates and exchange rates. At this capacities dividends worth \$5 million to \$14million can be paid to investors and shareholders. Per the analysis increasing the plant production capacity will increase the profitability of the plant.

It is also realized that keeping the levelized cost of energy above \$0.065 was realistic while charging \$0.085 and above was more ideal at 50% plant capacity. However, as the capacity gets closer to the maximum installed capacity the price can be reduced to \$0.045 and the financial outlook of the project would be good. In order to keep a low uniform price of \$0.045 throughout production levels, there will be the need of some sort of subsidy from the Government of Ghana to make the operations of the plant sustainable and viable. The calculated price point falls just within the estimated LCOE by Yankey *et al.* (2023) for solar plants in the country which is from \$0.04/kWh to \$0.15/kWh.

Finally, the cost of fuel when varied from \$0 upwards resulted in a decline of both NPV, IRR and dividends. Although the ideal situation is to have the cost of fuel at \$0 as the source of fuel is agricultural waste which is available in large quantities in the farming communities. Realistically for the analysis, a fuel cost of \$2M was assumed to cater for sudden demands from farmers. In worst case scenarios the operations of the plant will not be viable if fuel cost should exceed \$4M.

Potential Technologies

In view of the potential for the cost of obtaining fuel to increase, other readily available sources of waste can be considered. Municipal solid waste collected at waste sorting facilities could make use of the waste in generating electricity by combustion, gasification, pyrolysis and hydro thermal carbonization (Korneti, 2021). Making use of such waste can guarantee that the cost of fuel can be significantly reduced while at the same time reducing environmental pollution.

Policy Recommendations

1. Government through the Environmental Protection Agency must enforce their ban on open air burning. This would ensure that farmers do not hoard their waste and when subsequently overwhelmed resort to open air burning. By this policy farmers will be compelled to quickly give out their waste for other industrial activities.
2. Government should provide subsidies on energy prices and tax incentives to power producers within the renewable energy space to encourage more of such investments.
3. Government should ensure that there is access to low interest financing of such power plants.

Limitations of study

Due to time constraints and the word limit this analysis presented only three scenarios for the sensitivity analysis.

Recommendation for future research

Potential areas for future research (potential interventions and implementation challenges)
The scenarios tested is not exhaustive, therefore several other scenarios can be analyzed in future studies. Also, for future research, it would be interesting to see the interaction between the various scenarios. For example, how iterating plant production capacity, the LCOE and inflation rate would affect NPV, IRR shareholders dividends and other financial ratios .

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, the analysis established that for the proposed 30MW power plant to be financially viable, the minimum generation capacity allowed is 50%. ie 100GWh/year, the energy produced should be sold at \$0.085 to make maximum gains. It estimates that fuel cost for running operations should not exceed \$4M for good returns. The study suggests that other non conventional fuel sources such as MSW can be used in place of biomass sources. In terms of policy, environmental regulatory agencies must enforce their ban on open air burning and indiscriminate disposal of waste, make available low interest loans for financing renewable energy plants and finally provide subsidy on the estimated LCOE to make it profitable for both the generators and the consumers.

References

- Amuah, E. E. Y., Fei-Baffoe, B., Kazapoe, R. W., Dankwa, P., Okyere, I. K., Sackey, L. N. A., Nang, D. B., & Kpiebaya, P. (2024). From the ground up: Unveiling Ghana's soil quality crisis and its ecological and health implications. *Innovation and Green Development*, 3(1), 100097. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.igd.2023.100097>
- Arkorful, V. E. (2022). Unravelling electricity theft whistleblowing antecedents using the theory of planned behavior and norm activation model. *Energy Policy*, 160, 112680. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2021.112680>
- Bank of Ghana. (n.d.). *Bank of Ghana*. Bog.gov.gh. <https://www.bog.gov.gh/>
- Korneti, H. (2021). *Top Innovative Technologies In Waste-to-Energy*. Wwww.valuer.ai. <https://www.valuer.ai/blog/top-innovative-technologies-in-waste-to-energy>
- OECD. (n.d.). *Export credits - OECD*. Wwww.oecd.org. Retrieved from: <https://www.oecd.org/trade/topics/export-credits/>
- Ralls, E. (2023). *Game-changing invention converts both CO2 and plastic waste into renewable energy*. Earth.com. <https://www.earth.com/news/game-changing-invention-converts-both-co2-and-plastic-waste-into-renewable-energy/>
- Statista. (2018). Ghana - share of economic sectors in the gross domestic product 2008-2018 | Statista. Statista; Statista. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/447524/share-of-economic-sectors-in-the-gdp-in-ghana/>
- Mawusi S.K, Shrestha, P., Chen, X., & Liu, G. (2023). A comprehensive review of the production, adoption and sustained use of biomass pellets in Ghana. *Heliyon*, 9(6), e16416–e16416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e16416>
- United Nations. (2023, June 13). *With Climate Crisis Generating Growing Threats to Global Peace, Security Council Must Ramp Up Efforts, Lessen Risk of Conflicts, Speakers Stress in Open Debate* | UN Press. Press.un.org. <https://press.un.org/en/2023/sc15318.doc.htm>
- Yankey, B. E., Gyamfi, C., Arthur, E., Dekongmen, B. W., Asantewaa-Tannor, P., Tawiah, J. K., & Mends, L. G. (2023). Small hydropower development potential in the Densu River Basin, Ghana. *Journal of Hydrology: Regional Studies*, 45, 101304. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejrh.2022.101304>

Acknowledgements

This material has been produced with support from the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) programme. CCG is funded by UK aid from the UK government. However, the views expressed herein do not necessarily reflect the UK government's official policies.

Many thanks to Climate Compatible Growth, United Nations Energy Commission for Africa, Ministry of Energy Ghana, the Ghana Energy Commission, Ghana Atomic Energy Commission, Ghana Institute of Management and Public Administration, and The Brew-Hammond Energy Centre at Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology as well as the organizers of the EMP-A for making this training a success.

The understanding and appreciation of the FinPlan tool has been made possible by our main trainer Ms. Naomi Tan who has been very instrumental in developing our case studies. Her warmth and patience is very much appreciated. I also thank Robert William da Silva who has been of great help in completing this report. To all my colleagues in the FIPLAN track thank you all for the ideas and the encouragement.

